

THEATER OF MILITARY OPERATIONS: ANALYSIS OF MODERN CONFLICTS

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Abstract

The article analyzes the evolution of the concept of "theater of military operations" as a strategic category of military art. It examines the historical development of theater of military operations (TMO) preparation, its influence on the forms and methods of armed struggle, as well as the modern classification of theaters of military operations and their structural elements (strategic and operational directions, military-geographical regions). Special attention is paid to the role of military and dual-use infrastructure in ensuring state defense capability. The conclusion highlights the increasing importance of advance TMO preparation in the context of modern military conflicts.

Keywords: theater of military operations, military geography, operational equipping of territory, military infrastructure, dual-use infrastructure, advance preparation.

In modern conditions of geopolitical instability and the evolution of armed warfare means, the issues of preparing and equipping the theater of military operations are gaining particular significance. The quality of operational territory equipping and the development of military and dual-use infrastructure largely determine a state's ability to repel aggression in the initial period of conflict and successfully address strategic tasks. The study of the theater of military operations (hereinafter TMO) extends far beyond military issues and is closely linked to military geography, economics, logistics, and national security concerns [1].

Despite the history of theoretical developments, there is currently a gap between classical conceptions of the TMO and the realities of hybrid conflicts, high troop mobility, and the role of the aerospace and information spheres. Many elements of TMO preparation require rethinking in light of new threats and technologies.

Military specialists from different eras have noted that the level of development of TMO elements significantly influenced the choice of troop training methods, forms and methods of their combat employment, the nature of

battles, the organization of interaction, comprehensive support, and troop command and control.

Thus, the presence of developed operational territory equipping was of decisive importance for the development of the theory and practice of military art.

With the development of armed warfare means, approaches to preparing the theater of future military operations have also improved. The quality of military infrastructure largely determined the effectiveness of countering an aggressor and the ability to achieve goals already in the initial period of the conflict. At the same time, the study of military operations is not limited only to the analysis of armed struggle – "military geography" plays a crucial role, investigating the complex of military-geographical conditions in potential TMOs and their influence on the preparation and conduct of operations [2].

Certain separate parts of the globe, by virtue of their geographical position and strategic significance, can form independent "military-geographical regions," encompassing an entire continent or a large region with adjacent islands, ocean waters, and aerospace space.

Accordingly, "Objects in the TMO" are classified by degree of significance:

Objects of strategic significance – their destruction or capture leads to a radical change in the balance of forces (naval basing areas, strategic aviation, nuclear submarines, higher military command posts, major industrial and administrative centers, etc.).

Objects of operational significance – significantly influence the situation in an operational direction (operational-tactical missile units, tactical aviation, communication hubs, rear bases, etc.).

Objects of tactical significance – military towns, training grounds, training centers, etc. [1,2].

Based on the significance and role of modern military conflicts of 2022-2026, a radical transformation of the concept of "theater of military operations," introduced by A. Jomini in 1815, is clearly demonstrated. Whereas previously the TMO was understood as a relatively compact territory for the general battle of main forces, today it represents an extensive multidimensional space, including continental regions, the aerospace sphere, maritime areas, cyberspace, and civilian dual-use infrastructure [1].

Below is an extended comparative analysis of three key modern conflicts (see Table 1).

Special Military Operation Russia – Ukraine (2022-2026)

Type of TMO: Classical continental with elements of positional and maneuver warfare.

Spatial scale: Over 2,500 km of battle contact line, depth of operations up to 700-1,000 km (considering strikes against rear targets of both sides).

Key features of preparation and conduct of combat operations:

Massive use of various drones (FPV, reconnaissance, strike, "Geran-mopeds") has changed the nature of the tactical and operational levels;

The main target is dual-use infrastructure (power grid, railway hubs, ports, bridges, fuel depots);

Widespread use of minefields and fortifications (Surovikin lines, "dragon's teeth") has restored the classical significance of operational territory equipping from the 20th century, but at a new technological level [4];

Logistics and transport communications become decisive factors (control over river, rail, and highways determines the pace of an offensive).

Israel – Palestine (Gaza) Conflict (2023-2026)

TMO Type: Urban (hybrid) in conditions of extremely high population density, compact territory (approx. 365 km²), but with enormous depth of underground infrastructure (Hamas tunnels).

Key features:

Combat operations are conducted in dense urban areas, where civilian objects (hospitals, schools, residential buildings) simultaneously serve as elements of enemy military infrastructure.

Widespread use of underground communications (tunnel network), which sharply increases the importance of engineer territory equipping.

High importance of informational-psychological and humanitarian factors: every destruction of a dual-use object causes international resonance;

Constant alternation of ground operations, airstrikes, and special operations to eliminate Hamas command [3].

Iran – US-Israel Conflict (escalation 2025-2026)

TMO Type: Aerospace, naval forces with elements of strategic strikes deep into the country.

Scale: Strikes from the Strait of Hormuz to the Red Sea and Iranian territory (strike depth over 2,000 km).

Features of the conflict:

Struggle for "objects of strategic significance" – nuclear centers, missile silos, oil terminals, command posts, and air defense systems;

Precision weapons, hypersonic missiles, swarm drone attacks, and cyber operations enable strikes without inserting large US ground forces;

A key element is control over maritime communications (Strait of Hormuz) and disruption of oil and gas supplies;

Dual-use infrastructure (petrochemicals, ports, civilian airports) is used for both military and economic purposes, making it a priority target [5].

Table 1.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EXISTING CONFLICTS

Параметр	Russia - Ukraine	Iran - US/Israel	Israel - Palestine
Main TMO Type	Continental	Aerospace, naval	Urban, hybrid
Main Object of Struggle	Infrastructure and logistics	Strategic deep targets	Underground and urban infrastructure
Role of Drones	Massive	Swarm, precision	Tactical, reconnaissance
Significance of Dual-Use Infrastructure	Critically high	Decisive	Determining
Duration	Protracted positional	Short intensive campaigns	Cyclical

Based on the analysis and study of the TMO in modern conditions, it can exist practically without a classical front (defense) line. At the same time, strategic strikes deep into enemy territory and control over critically important infrastructure objects of states can accomplish the tasks of armed conflicts without territorial occupation.

Furthermore, when conducting military operations in urban conditions, concepts such as "front" and "rear" disappear from the TMO terminology. TMO preparation requires special methods for protecting and assaulting dual-use objects while minimizing civilian casualties. In the continental part of the TMO, the advance preparation of dual-use infrastructure (roads, energy, depots, etc.) can compensate for numerical enemy superiority and prolong the conflict indefinitely.

From the conclusions, it can be suggested that TMO preparation remains one of the most important factors in ensuring the military security of a state. In modern conditions, the development of "dual-use infrastructure," which allows

for the effective use of civilian objects in the interests of defense at minimal financial cost, acquires particular importance.

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